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CHEMICAL NANOENGINEERING

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UNRAVELING THE EXCITED-STATE DYNAMICS OF
[3.3]PARACYCLOPHANE USING SURFACE HOPPING

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Abstract

Paracyclophanes are stiff, three-dimensional frameworks in which two benzene rings are maintained in a parallel, stacked position by short aliphatic linkers. Their derivatives exhibit significant through-space electronic interactions when in the excited state. This study reveals the ultrafast excited-state dynamics of [3.3]Paracyclophane ([3,3]PCP) using time-dependent density functional theory and nonadiabatic molecular dynamics simulations via surface hopping. This work provides detailed insight into how this system evolves in the excited state during 2 ps dynamics. It investigates the impact of conformational changes on the distribution of electron density, as revealed by the analysis of the fragment-based transition density matrix. We reported on how this molecule relaxes from S3 to S1 minimum and how its electronic structure, excitation type, and charge transfer character change. In this study, we demonstrated how [3.3]PCP evolves in the excited states from a delocalized excitation (excitonic resonance) state with minor charge transfer (CT) character (≈ 0.2) to a mixed regime of excitonic resonance and charge-resonance states, characterized by a higher CT value (≈ 0.5).

Keywords: [3.3]Paracyclophane, Excited-state dynamics, Surface hopping, Cremer–Pople and Boeyens analysis, Fragment-based transition density matrix analysis

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1 Introduction

Photochemistry is the branch of chemistry that investigates the chemical and physical effects of light on matter¹. Its basis is the excitation of electrons from the ground electronic state to one or more excited states when photons are absorbed. The transiently populated excited states govern a vast variety of chemical processes, ranging from photosynthesis and biological vision to photovoltaic energy conversion and photochemical catalysis in materials science^{2,3}. The fundamental photochemistry rules, including the Grotthuss–Draper law (stating that only that light which is absorbed by a system can bring about a photochemical change)⁴ and the Stark–Einstein law (according to which for every photon of light absorbed by a chemical system, only one molecule is activated for a photochemical reaction)⁵, form the basis of understanding how molecules interact with light and change their energy levels.

Upon absorption of light, a molecule is promoted from the ground state (denoted by S_0 if the molecule has singlet multiplicity) to an electronically excited higher energy state (S_1 , S_2 , etc.). It initiates a series or chain of dynamical processes¹. They include radiative relaxation, such as phosphorescence, a photoluminescence process where an excited molecule in a triplet state (unpaired-electron spin multiplicity) decays to the singlet ground state by photon emission and fluorescence, a photoluminescence process where an excited molecule in a singlet state (paired-electron spin multiplicity) returns to the singlet ground state by emitting a photon⁶, nonradiative loss (intersystem crossing and internal conversion), photochemistry, and charge or energy transfer. The dynamics of such excited states occur on ultrafast timescales (picoseconds to femtoseconds) in the case of internal conversion, typically on the order of nanoseconds for fluorescence, and on longer timescales (up to milliseconds) in the cases of intersystem crossing and phosphorescence. They are controlled by the topography of the potential energy surfaces (PESs) associated with each electronic state⁷.

Classical models formerly viewed such transitions as independent vertical excitations and emissions (e.g., Franck–Condon principle), but the present firm conviction is that excited-state dynamics involve intricate nuclear–electronic coupling and rapid state-to-state processes⁸. The comprehension of these ultrafast phenomena has become essential not only in molecular biology and photochemistry but also in the development of functional materials, such as fluorescent probes, molecular switches, and light-harvesting devices^{2,9}.

Advances in quantum dynamics and theoretical photochemistry have expanded our ability to model and interpret these processes. Quantum chemical computations and time-resolved spectroscopies have highlighted the importance of minor modifications to molecular geometry and electronic structure during relaxation¹⁰. These are usually

stimulated by strong couplings among PESs and strongly depend on the vibronic structure¹¹.

One of the most significant developments in modern photochemistry has been the recognition of the pivotal role of nonadiabatic effects in excited-state processes. Traditionally, the Born–Oppenheimer approximation allowed for the separation of nuclear and electronic motion in quantum mechanical systems. While effective for ground-state phenomena, this approximation breaks down in excited-state dynamics where the potential energy surfaces of different electronic states approach one another closely¹².

Nonadiabatic transitions occur when the coupling between electronic and nuclear degrees of freedom becomes strong, especially near points where two or more electronic states are energetically degenerate or nearly so¹¹. In these regions, the nuclear wavepacket can efficiently transfer from one electronic state to another without emitting a photon, an essential mechanism behind internal conversion (IC) and intersystem crossing (ISC). The most notable of these crossings are conical intersections (CIs), geometric configurations where two PESs intersect and form a conical topology in the multidimensional nuclear coordinate space^{13,14}.

Conical intersections represent funnels through which excited-state population can rapidly and efficiently return to the ground state. These are not unusual anomalies but are instead ubiquitous in polyatomic molecules and play a central role in photoprotection (e.g., within DNA bases), photoisomerization (e.g., with retinal), and charge separation (e.g., in organic solar cells)^{15,16}.

Nonradiative transitions via conical intersections, unlike radiative decays, are very fast (often <200 fs), and therefore, they are the dominant channels in most photophysical processes¹⁵. In the vicinity of conical intersections (in case of the excited state to ground state), PESs exhibit strong curvature and coupling. This makes single-reference methods, such as time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT), unreliable in these areas¹⁷. Multireference methods, such as complete active space self-consistent Field (CASSCF) and multireference configuration interaction (MRCI), are often needed to correctly capture the electronic structure and transition dynamics at these points. Thus, the inclusion of nonadiabatic effects in molecular dynamics is necessary to accurately portray molecular behavior in the excited state¹⁸.

To describe the effects of the intricate couplings between electronic and nuclear motion beyond the Born–Oppenheimer approximation, nonadiabatic molecular dynamics (NAMD) has proven to be a valuable tool for this purpose. NAMD algorithms calculate real-time molecular dynamics on coupled potential energy surfaces, allowing for the incorporation of electronic transitions as well as the redistribution of energy within

vibrational modes¹⁹. Unlike static quantum chemical calculations, which offer a snapshot of electronic states at fixed geometries, NAMD tracks molecular motion through PES crossings and conical intersections, thereby unveiling the full dynamical picture of ultrafast photophysical and photochemical events¹⁸.

The most widely used approach in NAMD is surface hopping, particularly Tully's fewest-switches surface hopping (FSSH) algorithm²⁰. In FSSH, classical nuclear trajectories evolve on a single adiabatic PES at any given time. Still, they are allowed to stochastically hop to other PESs based on nonadiabatic coupling and transition probabilities. Modern implementations of FSSH typically incorporate decoherence corrections to mitigate overcoherence artifacts and better reflect the loss of electronic coherence after a hop²¹. This framework has been effectively employed in a wide range of systems, from small organic molecules to biomolecules and semiconductor nanostructures¹⁷. Machine learning and deep neural networks have been used in NAMD frameworks to reduce computational expense and increase usability for larger systems²².

NAMD has proven especially powerful in revealing mechanistic insights in processes such as:

- Photostability in nucleobases (rapid internal conversion via conical intersections)²
- Photoisomerization in vision proteins (cis-trans retinal dynamics)¹⁵
- Exciton migration and charge separation in organic photovoltaic materials¹⁶
- Ultrafast nonradiative decay in perovskites and quantum dots²³

These results not only enhanced our understanding of fundamental photophysics but also guided the rational design of light-activated materials. In materials science, for instance, the energetic alignment and coupling between states have become crucial in quenching unproductive nonradiative decay routes and maximizing the quantum efficiency of optoelectronic devices²⁴.

This thesis study explores the nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics of [3.3]paracyclophane, as shown in Figure 1, a derivative of the paracyclophanes (PCP) family.

Figure 1: Molecular structure of [3.3]Paracyclophane ([3.3]PCP).

Paracyclophanes are rigid, three-dimensional scaffolds in which two benzene rings are held in a parallel stacked orientation by short aliphatic bridges. This unique geometry forces donor (D) and acceptor (A) groups attached to opposite rings into close proximity yet electronically decoupled by saturated linkers. As a result, PCP derivatives exhibit pronounced through-space electronic interactions in the excited state²⁵. For instance, dithia[3.3]paracyclophane (the sulfur analogue of PCP) has emerged as an excellent 3D platform for controlling through-space donor–acceptor coupling²⁶. Dithia[3.3]paracyclophane represents a compelling molecular framework due to its ability to enforce close spatial proximity between aromatic rings, enabling through-space π – π interactions that are otherwise inaccessible in conventional linear conjugated systems. This structural feature has been leveraged in donor–acceptor architectures to finely tune charge-transfer dynamics and excited-state energetics, especially in the design of thermally activated delayed fluorescence (TADF) materials for OLEDs^{27,28}. The unique 3D geometry of the [3.3]PCP scaffold also makes it an ideal spacer in supramolecular assemblies and surface-grafted monolayers, where electronic decoupling between a substrate and an active chromophore is critical to preserve optical functionality²⁵.

In a groundbreaking study by Vázquez et al.²⁹, researchers showed that the two-molecule junction made from dithia[3.3]paracyclophane has a much higher conductance than its single-molecule version. The peak conductance of the parallel-pathway [3.3]PCP junction was found to be about 2.8 times greater than that of the single-backbone setup. This increase is much larger than the simple additive expectation of 2.0 times, which we would expect if the two conduction paths worked independently. Instead, the significant growth shows strong proof of constructive quantum interference from the coherent superposition of electron wavefunctions moving through both molecular backbones. This finding highlights how important molecular coherence is in controlling charge transport at the nanoscale and shows the possibility of designing quantum interference effects through molecular design.

Moreover, the forced π -stacking in the PCP structure and the consequent challenge of describing such a complex electronic configuration make these molecules ideal for probing the accuracy of novel theoretical methods.

Thus, in this thesis, I systematically study [3,3]PCP using both static and dynamic methods to explore its excited-state behavior. The work begins with a review of the theoretical background and computational approaches used in excited-state dynamics, followed by the presentation of simulation results. It concludes with a summary of the main findings.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Electronic Excited States

Photoinduced processes in molecules require a quantum mechanical description of the full system. The total energy of a molecule (including its electrons and nuclei) is described by the molecular Hamiltonian³⁰

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{j=1}^f \frac{\hat{p}_j^2}{2m_j} + \hat{H}_e(\mathbf{q}), \quad (1)$$

In this equation, q_j are the coordinates of the system, \hat{P}_j are the momentum operators, m_j are the masses of the f nuclear degrees of freedom (typically f is three times the number of atoms), and $\hat{H}_e(\mathbf{q})$ is the electronic Hamiltonian.

Under the Born–Oppenheimer approximation, one solves the electronic Schrödinger equation at fixed nuclear geometry to obtain eigenvalues $V_n(\mathbf{Q})$, which define the adiabatic PES of the n th electronic state³¹. Electronic excited states of molecules arise when electrons occupy higher-energy molecular orbitals than in the ground state. Each electronic state defines a PES, which is the electronic energy as a function of nuclear coordinates.

Quantum-chemical methods are used to compute the excited-state PES. In practice, the electronic Hamiltonian $\hat{H}_e(\mathbf{q})$ (containing electron kinetic and potential terms) is diagonalized at many nuclear geometries to map out $V_n(\mathbf{Q})$ ³¹. Widely used approaches include linear-response time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT), configuration interaction (CI), and multireference methods (e.g., CASSCF/CASPT2), which can capture the multi-configurational character of excited states. TD-DFT offers a practical balance of cost and accuracy and is by far the most commonly used method for excited-state calculations³². The resulting PES (ground and excited) form a manifold of valleys, peaks, and crossings that govern photochemical pathways.

2.2 Density Functional Theory (DFT) and Time-Dependent DFT

Density Functional Theory (DFT) is the most widely used computational chemistry method for calculating the electronic structure of atoms, molecules, and solids. It is based on the recognition that any property of a many-electron system can be accessed from its

electron density, rather than from its many-body electronic wavefunction. This fundamental principle was established by the Hohenberg–Kohn theorems, which state that the ground-state energy is a unique functional of the electron density $\rho(\mathbf{q})$, i.e., $E = E[\rho]$ ³³.

The foundation for DFT was laid with the Kohn–Sham formulation, as shown below, in equation 2, where a model system of non-interacting electrons is defined in such a way that it shares the same ground-state electron density as the interacting system. The electronic energy is then derived in terms of a sum of terms³⁴.

$$E[\rho] = T_s[\rho] + E_{ext}[\rho] + E_H[\rho] + E_{xc}[\rho] \quad (2)$$

where $T_s[\rho]$ is the non-interacting electron kinetic energy, $E_{ext}[\rho]$ is the interaction with the external potential (normally nuclei), $E_H[\rho]$ is the classical Coulomb repulsion (Hartree energy), and $E_{xc}[\rho]$ contains all the many-body exchange and correlation terms. As the exact form of the xc functional is not known, we rely on density functional approximations. Therefore, the quality of a DFT calculation hinges solely on the validity of the exchange–correlation functional employed. General-purpose methods include Local Density Approximation (LDA), Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA), B3LYP-type hybrid functionals, and range-separated hybrid functionals, such as CAM-B3LYP and ω B97X^{35,36}.

Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT) extends the success of DFT to the treatment of excited states. It has become an essential tool for calculating the optical and electronic properties of molecules and materials. TDDFT is rooted in the Runge–Gross theorem, the time-dependent counterpart of the Hohenberg–Kohn theorems. It posits that the time-dependent electron density $\rho(\mathbf{q},t)$ uniquely determines the time-dependent external potential and, by extension, the time-evolution of the quantum system^{37,38}.

In actual applications, TDDFT is generally used in the linear-response regime to calculate excited-state energies and transition properties³⁵. Within this scheme, the perturbation response of the system to a weak time-dependent perturbation (e.g., an external electromagnetic field) is calculated from ground-state Kohn–Sham orbitals. This results in an eigenvalue problem referred to as the Casida equations^{35,36}, which are presented in equation 3.

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ B^* & A^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \end{pmatrix} = \omega \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Here ω is the Excitation energy (eigenvalue), X and Y are Eigenvectors for the linear combination of single-particle (orbital) transitions, and A and B are Matrices formed from orbital energy differences and electron interaction terms. Matrices A and B can be further simplified as follows:

Matrix A elements: $A_{ia,jb} = \delta_{ij}\delta_{ab}(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_i) + K_{ia,jb}$

Matrix B elements: $B_{ia,jb} = K_{ia,jb}$

Where:

- i, j = occupied orbitals
- a, b = virtual (unoccupied) orbitals
- ϵ = Kohn–Sham orbital energies
- $K_{ia,jb}$ = coupling terms from Coulomb and exchange-correlation

One of the most natural interpretations of TDDFT is through the idea of resonance. When a molecule is excited by the absorption of a photon of definite frequency corresponding to the energy gap between two electronic states, it is brought into an excited state. This is analogous to classical resonance, in which a system most strongly absorbs energy at its natural frequency³⁸. TDDFT in the linear response approximation captures these resonances by examining how the oscillating electron density is created under the action of a time-dependent field. The maxima of the resulting absorption spectrum represent allowed electronic transitions and provide direct insight into the optical properties of the molecule³⁹.

To facilitate the computational process and improve numerical stability, particularly in spin-unstable systems or large basis sets, the Tamm–Dancoff approximation (TDA) is typically employed. TDA simplifies the Casida equations by excluding the coupling terms responsible for de-excitation processes (B matrix)^{36,40}, and the equation becomes:

$$AX = \omega X \quad (4)$$

Despite this simplification, TDA continues to represent the principal features of excited-state transitions and is used in many practical TDDFT calculations.

RI approximation (density fitting) is a method used for the simplification of the calculation of computationally expensive two-electron integrals. Instead of directly computing four-centre electron repulsion integrals, RI approximates the Coulomb interaction using an auxiliary basis set⁴¹. This approximation saves a substantial amount of computational expense and is particularly useful in large-scale DFT and TDDFT calculations.

2.3 Surface Hopping

In quantum molecular dynamics, regions of strong nonadiabatic coupling, such as conical intersections or avoided crossings, mark a breakdown of the Born–Oppenheimer approximation. In these regions, the electronic and nuclear degrees of freedom become intricately entangled, and transitions between potential energy surfaces cannot be

ignored. To accurately simulate these transitions, particularly in excited-state processes, it is essential to employ frameworks that incorporate both quantum and classical descriptions of motion. Among the various mixed quantum–classical approaches developed, surface hopping has emerged as one of the most widely adopted methods.

This approach allows classical nuclei to evolve on adiabatic potential energy surfaces while probabilistically switching electronic states based on computed nonadiabatic coupling vectors¹⁹. Surface hopping is a mixed quantum-classical algorithm where nuclei are treated classically while electrons are evolved quantum-mechanically. The concept was first introduced by Tully and Preston and later formalized in a practical and widely used variant known as the Fewest Switches Surface Hopping (FSSH) method, developed by John C. Tully in 1990^{20,42}.

FSSH aims to minimize the number of electronic state switches while still reproducing the correct quantum mechanical populations over time.⁴³ It is based on the idea that the system should hop between potential energy surfaces only when the transition probability, which is based on the electronic wavefunction dynamics, warrants it.

A core part of the FSSH algorithm is the computation of nonadiabatic coupling vectors (NACVs), which reflect the derivative of the electronic wavefunctions with respect to nuclear positions⁴⁴. The probability for a trajectory to hop from state i to state j in a time step Δt is given by:

$$g_{ij} = \frac{2\text{Re}(C_i^* C_j \mathbf{d}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{v})}{C_i^* C_j} \Delta t \quad (5)$$

where C_i and C_j are the amplitudes of the electronic states, \mathbf{d}_{ij} is the NACV, and \mathbf{v} is the nuclear velocity. Despite its wide use, FSSH is not without limitations. FSSH does not inherently account for decoherence, meaning it lacks a mechanism to naturally damp coherence between electronic states after a branching event. As a result, decoherence corrections, often introduced as empirical damping terms, are required to simulate the loss of electronic coherence during nonadiabatic transitions realistically⁴⁴.

To address the limitations of traditional Fewest Switches Surface Hopping (FSSH), several alternative formulations of nonadiabatic coupling have been proposed, aiming to reduce computational overhead and enhance accessibility. Among these, the time-dependent Baek-An (TDBA) coupling model represents a noteworthy advancement. This approach was introduced as a means to circumvent the explicit calculation of nonadiabatic coupling vectors (NACVs), which are often computationally demanding and may not be directly available in many electronic structure packages⁴³. The TDBA model approximates nonadiabatic couplings in one-dimensional systems by relating them to the curvature of the adiabatic energy gap between electronic states, as shown in Eq. 6.

In this framework, the coupling is inferred from the second derivative of the energy difference between the involved potential energy surfaces, offering a practical route to include nonadiabatic effects without invoking full quantum-mechanical derivative couplings⁴⁴.

$$h_{jl}(\mathbf{Q}) \approx \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\frac{d^2 \Delta E_{jl}(\mathbf{Q})}{d\mathbf{Q}^2}} \quad (6)$$

Where $h_{jl}(\mathbf{Q})$ is the approximate nonadiabatic coupling between adiabatic electronic states j and l , as a function of the nuclear coordinate \mathbf{Q} , \hbar is reduced Planck's constant, included to maintain the correct physical units and $\Delta E_{jl}(\mathbf{Q}) = E_j(\mathbf{Q}) - E_l(\mathbf{Q})$ is the Energy gap between the adiabatic electronic states j and l as a function of \mathbf{Q} .

In the context of surface hopping dynamics, TD-BA allows one to calculate time-derivative couplings directly as⁴³

$$\sigma_{jl}(t) \approx \frac{\text{sgn}(\Delta E_{jl})}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta E_{jl}} \frac{d^2 \Delta E_{jl}}{dt^2}} \quad (7)$$

Where $\sigma_{jl}(t)$ is the Time-derivative nonadiabatic coupling between states j and l , projected along the nuclear velocity vector. This is the quantity actually used in FSSH hopping probability calculations. $\text{Sgn } \Delta E_{jl}$ is the sign function, which returns +1 or -1 depending on whether $\Delta E_{jl} > 0$ or < 0 ; it ensures continuity in the sign of the coupling.

In surface hopping simulations, properly adjusting nuclear velocities after electronic state transitions is essential to ensure energy conservation and physically accurate dynamics. The most rigorous approach is to adjust velocities along the nonadiabatic coupling vector (h), which directly reflects the direction of the strongest electronic-nuclear interaction at the point of transition⁴⁵. However, computing h can be computationally expensive or unavailable in some methods. As an alternative, the gradient difference vector (g) provides a reliable and physically meaningful approximation and is generally more accessible in standard electronic structure calculations. When neither h nor g is available, a common fallback is to adjust velocities along the momentum direction (p). While simple and computationally inexpensive, this method can lead to unphysical artifacts, such as excessive back hoppings due to the large kinetic energy reservoir it draws from⁴⁶. To mitigate this, a modified approach known as p -direction with reduced kinetic energy (p -redKE) limits the energy available for adjustment by dividing it over the number of vibrational degrees of freedom.

3 Computational Methods

3.1 Quantum Chemical Calculations

Computational Electronic Structure calculations were performed for [3.3]paracyclophane to study the dynamics of excited states. Calculations for the ground state were performed using DFT with two functionals, CAM-B3LYP⁴⁷ and ω B97xD⁴⁸. Excited-state calculations were performed using linear-response TDDFT with these functionals. These calculations were performed using the quantum chemistry software Turbomole V7.6⁴⁹. All calculations were conducted with the basis set def-SV(P), which is similar to the 6-31G* basis set in Pople-style. The resolution of identity (RI) approximation was also employed in all calculations, as it is implemented in Turbomole, and it can significantly reduce computational cost. Long-range dispersion interactions (van der Waals forces) were accounted for using the DFT-D4 dispersion correction model⁵⁰ throughout the calculations.

Additional calculations were done using DFT-based multireference configuration interactions (DFT/MRCI)^{51,52}, algebraic diagrammatic construction to the second order (ADC(2))⁵³, MRCI based on the orthogonalization-and dispersion-corrected semiempirical method 3 (ODM3/MRCI)⁵⁴, and DFT-TDA using the CAM-B3LYP functional.

To check if there were any Interstate crossings (Conical intersections), we used CIOpt⁵⁵ software for optimizing the conical intersections. For the electron density analysis of our molecule, the TheoDORE⁵⁶ software was used.

3.2 Initial Conditions Generation

To start nonadiabatic dynamics, an ensemble of 1800 initial conditions was generated using a harmonic Wigner distribution centered around the optimized ground-state (S_0) minimum geometry, computed at the CAM-B3LYP/ def-SV(P)+D4 level of theory. For each sampled geometry, vertical excitation energies and oscillator strengths were calculated using the CAM-B3LYP+D4 functional and the def-SV(P) basis set. The initial condition generation was carried out using Newton-X CS⁵⁷, interfaced with Turbomole version 7.6.

3.3 Surface Hopping Dynamics

Nonadiabatic dynamics were performed using the Fewest Switches Surface Hopping (FSSH) method, including decoherence corrections through the simplified decay of mixing approach, with the parameter α set to 0.1 Hartree⁵⁸. Each simulation involved six electronic states (the ground state and five excited states) calculated using TDDFT at the CAM-B3LYP+D4/def-SV(P) level of theory.

The dynamics were run for up to 2 picoseconds, using a classical time step of 0.5 fs, resulting in up to 4000 single-point calculations per trajectory. A total of 100 trajectories were simulated. The time-dependent electronic Schrödinger equation was integrated with a smaller step of 0.025 femtoseconds, with electronic properties interpolated between classical steps to ensure smooth propagation. Different algorithms for evaluating frustrated hops and momentum rescaling were employed, as discussed later. In the case of frustrated hopping, momentum was kept in the original direction.

The dynamics was performed using Newton-X NS⁵⁷, interfaced with Turbomole version 7.6.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Single Point Calculations

It is good practice to perform static calculations to discuss the electronic properties of the molecule before studying the dynamics of the excited state. Thus, we began by optimizing the molecule at its ground state. Normal modes were calculated and checked to ensure that there were no imaginary(negative) frequencies, indicating a minimum. The IR spectrum is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Simulated IR spectrum of [3.3] PCP computed at the DFT level using the CAM-B3LYP/def2-SV(P)+D4 method.

Vertical excitation energies for the first 10 excited states for [3.3]paracyclophane were calculated using TDDFT (CAM-B3LYP/def-SV(P)+D4), TD-DFT (ω b97x/def-SV(P)+D4), DFT-TDA (CAM-B3LYP/def-SV(P)+D4), ADC(2), and DFT/MRCI (CAM-B3LYP/def-SV(P)+D4), as shown in Table 1.

Using multiple quantum chemistry methods is essential for finding a reliable and accurate method to describe your system. For instance, TDDFT in its conventional linear-response

form is primarily optimized for singlet-singlet excitations and often fails to describe triplet-triplet or singlet-triplet transitions, especially in systems with significant spin contamination or multireference character³⁴. To investigate if there were any doubly-excited states, triplet states, or singlet-triplet transitions, DFT/MRCI calculations were done. DFT/MRCI is a hybrid method that combines DFT orbitals with multireference configuration interaction, enabling accurate treatment of both singlet and triplet excited states, especially in cases where static correlation is significant³⁹. Furthermore, ADC(2), as a wavefunction-based method, includes electron correlation explicitly and can yield more accurate valence excitation energies than TDDFT for certain systems, especially when TDDFT suffers from charge-transfer or Rydberg state errors⁵⁹.

Across methods, low-lying states S_1 - S_5 generally exhibit negligible oscillator strengths, indicating dark excitations, while brighter transitions emerge from S_6 onward, most notably for S_6 and S_9/S_{10} . Excitation energies are systematically lower with DFT-MRCI and higher with TD- ω B97X relative to TD-CAM-B3LYP, with ADC(2) lying in between. TDDFT-TDA results closely follow full TDDFT values for both energies and oscillator strength, except for minor shifts (≤ 0.2 eV). The significant spread in f values for higher states (e.g., S_9 - S_{10}) suggests varying descriptions of transition character among methods, with TDDFT- ω B97X predicting particularly intense transitions for S_9 and S_{10} . DFT-MRCI showed no significant amount of double excitations among the low-lying states. The lowest doubly excited state is S_3 . The overall agreement is good, signaling that we can adopt TDDFT for proceeding with dynamics.

Table 1: Vertical excitation energies (ΔE) and oscillator strengths (f) for the first 10 singlet excited states for [3.3]paracyclophane.

S_i	TDDFT (CAM-B3LYP)		TDDFT (ω B97X)		ADC (2)		DFT-CI// CAM-B3LYP		TDDFT-TDA (CAM-B3LYP)	
	ΔE	f	ΔE	f	ΔE	f	ΔE	f	ΔE	f
S_1	4.68	0.000	4.82	0.000	4.52	0.000	4.32	0.000	4.73	0.000
S_2	5.06	0.000	5.28	0.000	5.1	0.002	4.9	0.008	5.21	0.000
S_3	5.41	0.006	5.44	0.006	5.32	0.000	4.96	0.000	5.45	0.005
S_4	5.61	0.000	5.88	0.000	5.79	0.000	5.42	0.000	5.83	0.000
S_5	5.77	0.000	6.02	0.000	5.99	0.000	5.56	0.000	5.97	0.000
S_6	6.12	0.122	6.17	0.110	6.23	0.203	5.92	0.160	6.31	0.123
S_7	6.42	0.001	7.05	0.015	6.67	0.016	6.20	0.001	6.41	0.003
S_8	6.67	0.001	7.25	0.103	6.81	0.059	6.43	0.004	6.63	0.002
S_9	6.93	0.013	7.29	0.551	7.04	0.132	6.63	0.041	6.89	0.011
S_{10}	7.10	0.061	7.38	1.340	7.17	0.052	6.89	0.000	7.09	0.008

4.2 Initial conditions and absorption spectrum

To generate initial conditions for excited-state dynamics, we used the Newton-X Classical Series (NX-CS) in combination with Turbomole, following a workflow adapted from the official Newton-X tutorial. Geometry optimization and frequency calculations were performed at the DFT(CAM-B3LYP)/def-SV(P)+D4 level to obtain the equilibrium geometry and normal modes of the molecule. These vibrational data were used to generate an ensemble of nuclear geometries and momenta through Wigner distribution sampling, capturing the quantum zero-point vibrational motion in the ground electronic state.

To simulate the absorption spectrum, we used the Newton-X spectrum generation module in combination with TDDFT(CAM-B3LYP)/def-SV(P)+D4 electronic structure calculations. The spectrum was constructed using an ensemble of nuclear geometries and momenta sampled from a Wigner distribution. For each geometry, vertical excitation energies and oscillator strengths were computed. The individual electronic transitions were broadened using a Gaussian function with a width of 0.05 eV, and the intensity normalization was carried out based on the local statistical weight of the ensemble.

To explore the role of individual excited states in net absorption, the spectra were first simulated in isolation for the S_3 and S_6 states, as shown in Figure 3, so that their respective spectral signatures could be understood. A more detailed spectrum was then built by including all the ground-state (S_0) to the first nine singlet excited-state transitions (S_1 – S_9). These simulations enabled a highly resolved, state-resolved analysis of the absorption profile, capturing both the vibrational and electronic richness of the system.

Figure 3: Absorption spectrum of S₃, S₆, and the Total spectrum of S₁-S₉. The vertical axis is the absorption cross section in Å²/molecule.

The absorption spectrum of [3.3]PCP was simulated using the nuclear ensemble approach, considering excitations into the first nine singlet excited-state transitions (S₁–S₉). The spectrum displays two main bands (Figure 3). The dominant band, centered at ~6.1 eV, originates from the bright S₆ transition, as evident from the spectrum that considers excitations into this state exclusively. A weaker band appears at ~6.6 eV and is attributed to higher excited states (S₇–S₉). In addition, the main 6.1 eV band exhibits a shoulder on its low-energy side at ~5.5 eV, arising from the S₃ state. The partial overlap of the S₃ and S₆ contributions suggests a less distinct state separation, with the band shape changes likely reflecting differences in vibronic coupling or transition character⁶⁰.

These results provide insight into the photophysical behavior of the system, identifying S₆ as a dominant absorbing state at higher photon energies, while S₃ may play a more significant role in lower-energy excitation pathways.

4.3 Surface Hopping Dynamics

The simulation protocol followed the procedures outlined in the Newton-X tutorial and was adapted to use TDDFT at the CAM-B3LYP/def-SV(P)+D4 level of theory. Initial conditions were generated using a Wigner distribution based on ground-state vibrational modes. The initial conditions were selected within the interval of 5.00 to 5.50 eV, centered at 5.25 eV (± 0.25 eV). To ensure physical relevance, only initial conditions corresponding to excited states with significant oscillator strengths were retained.

The dynamics simulations were initiated in the S₃ state (the third singlet excited state), which was chosen based on its non-zero oscillator strength. Each trajectory was allowed

to evolve among the first five singlet excited states (S_1 – S_5). To estimate the nonadiabatic couplings required for surface hopping, the simulations employed the time-dependent Baek-An (TD-BA)³⁸ scheme with momentum adjustment in the full kinetic energy direction. The TD-BA method, described in detail in Section 2.3, estimates time-derivative nonadiabatic couplings based solely on the second time derivative of the adiabatic energy gap, making it particularly useful in electronic structure methods like TDDFT, where explicit nonadiabatic coupling vectors are not directly available.

The time evolution of electronic state populations reveals the excited-state relaxation pathway following initial photoexcitation, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Mean population decay over time obtained with surface hopping dynamics using adjustment in the momentum direction with full K.E.

The system begins in the S_3 state at time zero, as this state was selected based on its high oscillator strength (first bright state). Almost immediately, the S_3 population drops sharply, indicating ultrafast internal conversion, which occurs within approximately 50–70 fs.

Following this rapid decay, S_1 (blue line) becomes the primary population sink, with its average population stabilizing around 0.35–0.4 for most of the simulation duration. This means that S_1 is the dominant long-lived excited state, where most of the wave packet resides after nonadiabatic relaxation. The S_2 state (orange trace) also absorbs some population early following excitation, but it is always below S_1 , which implies a less significant role in the relaxation process.

Notably, the ground state S_0 remains nearly unoccupied in the first half of the simulation. Still, it gradually increases after ~ 500 fs, indicating that internal conversion to the ground state is a relatively slow process in this system. The population of S_0 becomes about 0.3 at the termination of the simulation, reflecting partial relaxation to the ground state within the timescale of 2 ps. This retarded rise indicates that recovery in the ground state is slower, presumably through $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transitions.

Higher excited states (S_4 – S_6) exhibit only transient populations, consistent with rapid depopulation and negligible reoccupation. Altogether, the dynamics reveal a stepwise decay pathway: $S_3 \rightarrow S_2 \rightarrow S_1 \rightarrow S_0$, and S_1 serving as the major intermediate and kinetic trap within the simulated 2 ps timescale.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the surface hopping simulations, convergence of energy was carefully monitored over all trajectories for the duration of the dynamics, as shown in Figure 5. Because hopping probabilities and nuclear forces directly depend on electronic state energy differences, any non-converged single-point calculation can result in significant errors, e.g., ill-defined hopping events, unphysical forces, or potential energy surface discontinuities.

Figure 5: Total energy for all trajectories over time to check the overall conservation of energy.

Moreover, statistical analysis of results and observables, such as excited-state populations and decay time constants, relies on consistent and physically meaningful data across the entire ensemble. By enforcing strict classical energy conservation criteria, the simulations maintain numerical stability and physical consistency, thereby ensuring that the computed dynamics reflect actual molecular behavior rather than artifacts of poor electronic structure calculations.

To investigate how our system transitions between electronic states, we draw a histogram of the hopping data, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Histogram showing the total number of hops between each pair of states from the surface hopping dynamics using the full K.E. approximation.

As we discussed earlier, the full kinetic energy was used to compensate for the potential energy difference between the two electronic states. If the system hops to a lower energy state, the velocity is increased to conserve total energy⁶¹. If it hops upward, the velocity is reduced.

As we can see from the histogram plot, this approach can artificially allow too many back hops (from low to high energy states), especially in large molecules, because all vibrational modes contribute to the kinetic energy reservoir. This causes a size-consistency artifact, which means the simulation outcome may incorrectly depend on the size of the molecule⁴⁶.

To mitigate this, the reduced kinetic energy (p-redKE) approach^{46,62} was adopted to limit the energy reservoir to the average kinetic energy per degree of freedom, offering a more physically realistic approximation⁶². This correction improves the accuracy of momentum-based velocity adjustments, especially in systems where more accurate directions, like the nonadiabatic coupling vector (\mathbf{h}) or gradient difference vector (\mathbf{g}), are unavailable.

Instead of using all the system's kinetic energy, the energy reservoir is scaled down as:

$$T_{\text{redKE}} = \frac{K}{N_{DF}} \quad (8)$$

Where:

- K is the total kinetic energy before the hop.
- N_{DF} is the number of vibrational degrees of freedom.

It prevents excessive back hopping by mimicking the effect of using a localized energy contribution, as would naturally occur if a nonadiabatic coupling vector (\mathbf{h}) were used. It avoids the size-consistency problem while retaining a simple and computationally cheap momentum-based direction.

Figure 7: Mean population decay over time obtained from surface hopping dynamics using adjustment in the momentum direction with Reduced K.E.

The implementation of the new approximation (adjustment in the momentum direction with Reduced K.E) showed quite a big difference in the populations of the excited state (Figure 7). As shown, the system undergoes ultrafast relaxation within the first 100 fs, characterized by rapid depletion of the S_3 population. Immediately after excitation, S_3 exhibits a sharp drop from full occupation to near zero, with a lifetime estimated to be <50 fs. This rapid decay reflects strong nonadiabatic coupling and efficient internal conversion to lower-lying singlet states. Following this, S_1 (blue curve) emerges as the dominant long-lived excited state. The occupation of S_1 rises steeply within the first 200 fs, reaching a stable average of ~ 0.9 , where it remains for the rest of the simulation window (up to 2000 fs). This indicates that S_1 acts as the primary electronic reservoir, effectively trapping most of the excited-state population.

Similarly, the histogram for the hopping data also showed that the number of back hops decreased significantly, as expected, in addition to the total number of transitions, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The histogram shows the total number of hops between each pair of excited states for surfacing hopping dynamics using the Reduced K.E. approximation.

In addition to the changes in the excited state population and back-hopping stats, we also observed that the trajectories going to the ground state S_0 have significantly decreased. They were around 30% in the previous dynamics (with momentum adjustment in the full kinetic energy direction) and now around 10%, which indicates that our system might not have Interstate-Crossings (Conical Intersections) that we suspected in the first dynamics.

In principle, this approximation should yield better results than the full-kinetic energy approximation. However, it might scale down our system's energy reservoir, leaving our system with less kinetic energy than it should have in reality. The best way to approximate that is to adjust in the direction of the gradient difference vector (\mathbf{g}) when the nonadiabatic coupling vector (\mathbf{h}) is unavailable. The primary limitation of using the gradient difference vector (\mathbf{g}) method lies in its computational cost, as it requires the evaluation of energy gradients for multiple electronic states at every time step of the dynamics. This effectively multiplies the computational effort compared to single-state calculations. To address this issue, Newton-X offers an optimization option that bypasses the computation of gradient differences during regular propagation and evaluates them only when a hopping event occurs.

We implemented this available option in NewtonX for Nonadiabatic dynamics to simulate the time-evolution of [3.3]PCP; the population of our molecule over time is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Average population decay over time from surface hopping dynamics using momentum rescaling along the gradient difference vector (\mathbf{g}).

The implementation of the new approximation (using the gradient difference vector (\mathbf{g})) showed almost similar results to those we got from the approximation of adjustment in the momentum direction with Reduced K.E. We could see that the population curves showed more fluctuations as compared to the Reduced K.E. approximation. It means that the system has more hops, as shown in Figure 10, than it did in the previous dynamics, as we discussed earlier. The Reduced K.E. approximation can scale down the energy reservoir of the system more than it should, which could cause a lower number of hops.

Figure 11: Energy gap at the time of hopping events $S_2 \rightarrow S_1$ or $S_1 \rightarrow S_2$, to analyze the distribution of energy gaps between these states at hop events.

The energy difference histogram for the actual hopping events between S_2 and S_1 (Figure 11) is peaked strongly at around 0.05–0.10 eV, and nearly all hops occur at gaps below 0.3 eV. This is expected in surface hopping algorithms, which are most likely to occur for transitions when the energy gap between states is smallest, thereby maximizing nonadiabatic coupling. Cumulatively, these findings are in accord with a mechanistic picture where the wavepacket initially in S_3 is ultrafast relaxed to S_2 and subsequently reversibly travels with S_1 , including hopping being restricted to geometries wherein the S_1 – S_2 gap decreases below ~ 0.2 eV. The local coupling regions, rather than the average gap, therefore, govern the population flow between excited states, justifying the use of local, trajectory-based nonadiabatic methods, such as surface hopping, in this context.

To model the kinetics of ground-state repopulation, the time evolution of the S_0 population was fitted using a single-exponential growth function with a delayed onset. The chosen model takes into account the fact that the S_0 population remains flat for an initial period, followed by a smooth, asymptotic increase. The fitting function is defined as:

$$P(t) = A \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{\tau}} \right) \quad (9)$$

where $P(t)$ is the S_0 population at time (t) , t_0 is the onset time at which the population begins to rise, and τ is the time constant characterizing the rate of population growth. This model assumes complete relaxation to the ground state (final population = 1.0) and

was selected to reflect the behavior observed in surface hopping dynamics, where nonadiabatic transitions are delayed and state-specific.

Figure 12: Plot of Exponential Fit To S_0 Population with lower and upper bounds of confidence interval for the mean population of S_0 .

Fitting the S_0 occupation with Eq. (9) yielded an onset time of $t_0 \approx 0.13$ ps and a lifetime of $\tau \approx 19$ ps (Figure 12), indicating that ground-state recovery is a relatively slow process. Because the simulations were limited to 2 ps, this value represents an extrapolation rather than a directly sampled decay. To estimate its reliability, we applied bootstrap analysis to compute the 95% confidence interval, yielding bounds of 12–23 ps. The long time constant for S_0 population growth reflects the kinetically hindered nature of $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ internal conversion, indicating that while nonadiabatic relaxation from initially excited S_3 state occurs within 0.1 ps, ground-state recovery is the slowest step in the relaxation cascade. This is consistent with a bottlenecked relaxation pathway dominated by S_1 trapping⁶³, requiring tens of picoseconds to fully repopulate the ground state.

The number of trajectories that went to S_0 was the same as we observed during the previous dynamics (p-redKE) approach. To verify if there were accessible Interstate crossings (Conical Intersections) in our system, we performed Minimum-Energy Conical Intersection Optimization Using Penalty Function Formalism with software called CIOpt⁶⁴. CIOpt implements a conical intersection optimization method based on the penalty function formalism proposed by Levine et al.⁶⁵, driving the energy difference between states toward zero while minimizing energy, designed to avoid the computationally expensive use of derivative coupling vectors and Hessians.

We selected one of the trajectories that was stopped before completion, indicating it entered a region of nonadiabaticity between the S_1 and S_0 , and started the Conical Intersection Optimization from the point where it was stopped. After optimization, the shortest gap between S_0 and S_1 was found to be 0.0009 au, or 0.02 eV. The geometry related to that gap is given in Figure 13B in comparison to the optimized ground state geometry (13A).

Figure 13: (A) S_0 minimum geometry, (B) Last geometry after CI optimization

We could see that there was puckering of the carbon atoms of both benzene rings, which are attached to side chains, and it appeared as though they were almost forming a 5-member SP_3 carbon ring.

To gain further insight into the energetic connectivity between the structures, we performed a Linear Interpolation in Internal Coordinates (LIIC) scan to assess whether there is an energy barrier along the path connecting them⁶⁶ as shown in Figure 14. LIIC is a technique for generating a path between two molecular geometries (typically, two stationary points, in our case, the S_0 minimum and a CI, as shown in Figure 11) by linearly interpolating the atomic coordinates⁶⁷. It provides an easy way to visualize and understand how the potential energy surfaces (PESs) of different electronic states approximately behave as a molecule moves from one geometry to another. It is handy for verifying CI optimizations and gaining insight into electronic structure changes along a reaction path.

Figure 14: Linear interpolation in internal coordinates (LIIC) from S_0 to CI optimized geometry

The results of the linear interpolation between the ground-state minimum and the final geometry obtained from conical intersection (CI) optimization using the CIOpt software provided key insights into the nature of electronic state crossings in [3.3]paracyclophane. The LIIC plot showed a pronounced narrowing of the energy gap between the S_0 and S_1 states toward the final geometry, suggesting proximity to an Interstate crossing. However, the two states do not become exactly degenerate along the path, indicating that the LIIC does not pass directly through a CI seam⁶⁸. This is consistent with the theoretical understanding that conical intersections lie on a two-dimensional branching space within the full nuclear coordinate space, and are therefore rarely encountered by simple linear scans or interpolations⁶⁹. The scan shows the S_2/S_1 crossing at much lower energy than the S_1/S_0 crossing, so it is kinetically much slower to get there. It is also possible that the decay events were influenced by artifacts such as zero-point energy (ZPE) leakage, a known issue in classical and semiclassical dynamics simulations, where vibrational energy from quantized high-frequency modes inappropriately leaks into lower-frequency modes or reaction coordinates, potentially causing unphysical hopping events or dynamical instability⁷⁰.

Additionally, since the optimization and dynamics were carried out using time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT), a single-reference method that lacks the multireference character necessary to accurately describe near-degenerate regions, such as conical intersections (CIs), the near-degeneracy observed at the endpoint must be interpreted with caution⁷¹. A more reliable confirmation of the CI would require multireference methods, such as CASSCF or CASPT2, which are capable of properly resolving nonadiabatic couplings and CI topologies.

4.4 Ring Puckering Analysis

Cremer-Pople analysis is a method for quantifying and describing the three-dimensional shape and puckering of cyclic molecules. It breaks down the ring's conformation into a set of parameters (called puckering coordinates)⁷², which describes the distortion or puckering of the ring compared to a perfect flat or chair shape. The puckering of six-membered rings is commonly described using the Cremer-Pople formalism, later refined by Boeyens⁷³, in terms of three spherical coordinates: the puckering amplitude Q , and the angular parameters θ and ϕ .

To investigate how our molecule behaves throughout the dynamics following photoexcitation, we examine the structural evolution of the Upper ring and Lower ring, as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Division of [3.3]PCP for Cremer-Pople and Boeyens analysis.

Cremer-Pople analysis was conducted independently for each six-membered ring at each time step throughout the full simulation time for all trajectories using Ulamdyn⁷⁴. The following results, shown in Figure 16, highlight the most significant conformations observed during the excited-state dynamics. From the heatmap (Figure 16-A) of puckering parameter amplitude (Q), we can see that the mean puckering was observed to be 0.18 Å, but values between 0.05 and 0.25 Å are often observed. The distribution is symmetric, as expected. It illustrates how the puckering degree in one ring correlates with that in the other ring. Only conformations with a puckering amplitude (Q) greater than 0.05 Å were considered to ensure meaningful deviations from planarity. For planar structure, we considered only those whose puckering amplitude was less than 0.05 Å.

Figure 16: (A) Heatmap of puckering amplitude Q for both (upper and lower) rings. (B) Histograms showing the results of Cremer-Pople and Boeyens analysis for both Rings for all trajectories over all times.

As shown in the histograms, a variety of puckered conformations like Boat (B), Twisted-Boat (T), Skew-Boat (S) and Envelope like (E) were observed, with a strong dominance of the boat-type conformation. For clarity, we adopt an ortho/meta/para notation for puckering atoms relative to the para-substitution pattern of benzene, grouping all symmetry equivalent conformations into the same class; for instance, $B_{2,5}$ is denoted $B_{p,p}$, 3S_2 as mS_p , and 6T_2 as oT_p .

Figure 16 highlights the most significant conformations observed during the excited-state dynamics. $B_{p,p}$, with C2 and C5 puckered toward the opposite ring, dominates. Other significant conformers include the twist-boat (mT_p) and envelope-like forms (E_p), both of which have atoms 2 or 5 puckered toward the opposite ring. The presence of multiple distinct puckering conformations involving C2 or C5 puckering suggests a restricted conformational flexibility during the dynamics. In fact, the dominant dimer conformation is ${}^{p,p}B-{}^mT_p$ (31k occurrences out of 387k structures analyzed), followed by ${}^{p,p}B-{}^mS_p$ (24k), ${}^{p,p}B-B_{p,p}$ (23k), and ${}^{p,p}B-E_p$ (14k). Fully planar conformers have a meager 529 occurrences.

4.5 Fragment-Based Transition Density Matrix Analysis

Although the Cremer-Pople and Boeyens analysis provides a clear picture of the geometric flexibility of the six-membered rings in [3.3]paracyclophane during excited-state dynamics, it does not provide information regarding the changes in electronic structure that accompany these conformational changes. To gain further insight into the molecule's behavior, it is necessary to investigate how electron density and excitonic character evolve along the trajectory. For this purpose, we employed TheoDORE⁵⁶, a

wavefunction analysis package that allows us to quantify the nature of electronic excitations and their spatial distribution.

We investigated how electronic density and excitonic character evolve by analysing the 1-electron transition density (1TDM). We analyzed the 1TDM distribution into four fragments: Fragments 1 and 2 are the two benzene rings, and Fragments 3 and 4 are the side chains. This division allowed us to assess the individual contribution of each fragment to electronic excitation.

We chose 28 points (10 points with equal intervals in the first 200 fs, as most state transitions occur within this time frame, and 18 points from the next 1800 fs, with equal intervals) during the dynamics to investigate how the charge character of the excited states changes. Two TheoDORE descriptors, CT (charge transfer) and POS (excitation position), were monitored at all chosen time steps for all Trajectories. POS tells you the average position of the excitation (center of hole/electron distribution), and the CT value gives you an idea of how much of the excitation involves electron-hole separation.

From the data obtained from the Ω -matrix (fragment-based charge transfer matrix) averaged over all trajectories, we can observe that the contribution to electronic excitation from side chains to rings or from side chains to side chains was almost negligible, and nearly all the contribution came from benzene rings. At time zero, the Ω -matrix is dominated by large diagonal elements (Ω_{11} and Ω_{22}), as shown in Figure 17. Concurrently, the off-diagonal terms (Ω_{12} and Ω_{21}) are nearly zero, consistent with a low charge transfer (CT) state. It implies that initially, [3,3]PCP is excited into an excitonic resonance state across both rings of the type $|\psi_{ER}\rangle \propto |R_1^*R_2\rangle + |R_1R_2^*\rangle$.⁷⁵

Figure 17: Average Ω values for all Trajectories over time for the Current (Occupied) state

Within the first 200 fs, a notable shift occurs: Ω_{11} and Ω_{22} decrease sharply to values around 0.22–0.25, while Ω_{12} and Ω_{21} increase significantly, reaching values around 0.15–0.18. This redistribution of Ω elements indicates the onset of inter-fragment electronic coupling, resulting in a transition from excitonic resonance to a state with increased charge-transfer character. The symmetry of the Ω -matrix elements, namely $\Omega_{11} \approx \Omega_{22}$ and $\Omega_{12} \approx \Omega_{21}$, means that the molecule is a state with mixed excitonic resonance ($|\psi_{ER}\rangle \propto |R_1^*R_2\rangle + |R_1R_2^*\rangle$) and charge-resonance ($|\psi_{CR}\rangle \propto |R_1^+R_2^-\rangle + |R_1^-R_2^+\rangle$) characters. These observations are corroborated by the 1TDM descriptors, which show a corresponding increase in the charge transfer (CT) value from ~ 0.2 to ~ 0.5 , shown in Figure 18. The excitation position (POS) stabilizes near 1.70, indicating that the spatial separation between the hole and electron reaches a quasi-equilibrium early in the dynamics.

In the later stage (200–2000 fs), all observables become saturated, signaling the establishment of a stable-state regime of excitation. Ω -matrix elements remain balanced and symmetric, namely $\Omega_{11} \approx \Omega_{22}$ and $\Omega_{12} \approx \Omega_{21}$, which corresponds to a stable mixture of excitonic resonance and charge-resonance (CR) state. This is backed by the Ω -matrix elements: significant contributions from Frag1 \rightarrow Frag1 and Frag2 \rightarrow Frag2 (each ~ 0.25) reflect delocalized excitonic transitions on both π -systems, while nearly equal contributions from Frag1 \rightarrow Frag2 and Frag2 \rightarrow Frag1 indicate simultaneous inter-fragment electron-hole exchange. This symmetric, delocalized coupling across fragments can be described as a charge-resonance-like state, defined here as a superposition of two opposing charge-transfer configurations coexisting with excitonic character. The constancy of CT and POS further supports this interpretation, pointing to a long-lived, delocalized, and partially charge-separated electronic structure.

Figure 18: Mean CT values for all Trajectories over time for the Current State. (C) Mean POS values for all Trajectories over time for the Current State.

To further investigate this, we calculated the values of the POS and CT TheoDORE descriptors for the S_1 minimum geometry. We observed that the values for CT (~ 0.45) and POS (~ 1.67) for the first excited state are nearly the same as those recorded during the dynamics from 200 fs to 2000 fs, as shown in Figure 18.

Natural Transition Orbital (NTO) analysis of the third excited state (S_3), which corresponds to the first bright singlet state at the S_0 minimum geometry shown in Figure 19. It reveals a moderately delocalized excitation with hybrid character (a combination of the different $\pi - \pi^*$ excitations of the two rings). The leading three NTO pairs contribute 34%, 31%, and 23% respectively, cumulatively accounting for $\sim 88\%$ of the total transition. This indicates a moderately mixed excitation that cannot be captured by a single orbital transition alone.

Figure 19: NTOs of S3 for the [3.3] PCP at the S0 minimum geometry (level of TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP-D4)

The character of the S₁ state at its minimum geometry was analyzed using Natural Transition Orbitals (NTOs) as shown in Figure 20. This analysis revealed a single dominant excitation, with a leading pair contributing 86% of the transition density.

Figure 20: NTOs of S1 for the [3.3] PCP at the S1 minimum geometry (level of TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP-D4)

A moderate charge transfer value ($CT \approx 0.45$) indicates some separation between the electron and hole across the fragments. The excitation position ($POS \approx 1.65$) confirms that the excitation is both spread out and extended spatially. The spatial overlap of the

NTOs indicates strong coupling between the fragments without complete localization. This shows a delocalized excitation characterized by partial charge transfer and charge resonance.

5 Photophysical fate of [3.3]PCP

Once [3.3]PCP is photoexcited by absorbing light in the ultraviolet (UV) region, it undergoes a cascade of ultrafast nonadiabatic transitions that funnel the population down to S_1 . Immediately following vertical excitation (within a few tens of femtoseconds or less), the wave packet on S_3 encounters a nonadiabatic crossing to S_2 . This ultrafast transition from S_3 to S_2 is facilitated by strong vibronic coupling and the narrow energy gap between these states at the Franck–Condon geometry. The population that reaches S_2 is further funneled into S_1 on a timescale of less than 100 fs. Once the molecule reaches S_1 , a notable change occurs as the decay slows dramatically. The S_1 state has a much longer lifetime compared to the higher states. In our simulations, a significant fraction of the trajectories remained in S_1 for hundreds of femtoseconds or even several picoseconds before returning to the ground state. This reflects a kind of bottleneck or trapping: S_1 is a long-lived excited state in [3.3]PCP. Experimentally and theoretically, excimer states are known to exhibit extended lifetimes on the order of tens of picoseconds in analogous π -stacked systems⁷⁶.

Once in S_1 , the population becomes kinetically trapped. Surface hopping simulations showed that S_1 retains over 85% of the population throughout the 2 picoseconds simulation window. This finding indicates that internal conversion to the ground state (S_0) occurs much more slowly. The fitted S_0 population growth curve yielded a time constant of approximately 18.6 ps, underscoring the delayed recovery of the ground state. This suggests that S_1 acts like a long-lived excimer-like state, stabilized by through-space π – π interactions between the two stacked benzene rings.

The slow $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ decay was linked to the need for significant molecular distortion to reach a conical intersection. Optimizing the minimum-energy S_0/S_1 crossing (Conical Intersection Optimization) revealed that the decay involves puckering of benzene rings into a boat shape, which aligns with known $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ decay pathways in benzene⁷⁶. Linear interpolation between the S_0 minimum and the CI-optimized geometry demonstrated a narrowing of the S_1 – S_0 gap toward about 0.02 eV, confirming that it is close to a nonadiabatic crossing region.

Wavefunction analysis provided more insight into the change in electronic character. Initially, S_3 exhibited an excitonic resonance or delocalized excitation character as well as minor charge transfer (CT) across both rings. As the geometry distorted toward the S_1 minimum, the excitation shifted into a moderate charge-transfer (CT) state, leading to

charge separation between the two rings. The charge-transfer value increases from approximately 0.2 to 0.5 across both rings, indicating the formation of a delocalized, coherent exciton with partial charge-resonance character, which might be the reason why this molecule has coherent electron transport, as shown in the study by Vázquez et al.²⁹, and the excitation position stabilized at about 1.7 Å, indicating greater electron–hole separation. This electronic asymmetry matched the geometric distortion seen during the dynamics, showing a strong connection between structure and state character.

6 Conclusions

This research explored the behaviour of [3.3]PCP in its excited states using a blend of TDDFT calculations, nonadiabatic dynamics, and one-electron transition density analysis. Key analysis of vertical excitations showed S_3 as the initial bright state, which undergoes a rapid relaxation sequence through S_2 into the lower-lying S_1 state. The dynamics of the population showed that S_1 functions as a long-lasting excited-state sink, holding the majority of the population throughout the 2 ps simulation duration.

The time it takes to return to the ground state was measured by modelling the growth of the S_0 population, resulting in a lengthy time constant (~18.6 ps), indicating weak nonadiabatic coupling at the S_1/S_0 interface. TheoDORE descriptors monitored the changes in excitation character during relaxation, highlighting the shift from delocalized excitonic characteristics to a mixture of excitonic resonance and charge resonance-like distribution.

In summary, this study presents a thorough computational framework for comprehending excited-state evolution in coupled chromophoric systems. The methodology applied here, integrating real-time dynamics with fragment-resolved analysis, presents a widely applicable approach for investigating nonradiative decay and state characteristics in other conjugated or through-space charge-transfer molecular systems.

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8 ANNEXES

Raw data for all three dynamics calculations, including gradient-difference vector (**g**), momentum direction with reduced kinetic reservoir (**p-redKE**), and full momentum direction (**p**), is available [here](#).